

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF ROLE OF PLASMA OBESTATIN LEVELS IN
OBESITY WITH RELATION TO DAILY LIFE STYLE IN
PAKISTANI POPULATION**Muhammad Adil Nawaz¹, Khalida Qasim², Muhammad Adnan Sarwar³¹Rural Health Centre Tibbi Qaisrani District Dera Ghazi Khan, ²District Headquarter Hospital Vehari, ³District Headquarter South City Hospital Okara.**Article Received:** August 2019**Accepted:** September 2019**Published:** October 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Obesity is a pathological condition, which results from an imbalance between caloric intake and expenditure, and is characterized by excessive body fat accumulation, that has severe impact on life quality and life expectancy due to the burden of associated co-morbidities.

Aims of the study: The main aim of the present study is to analyze the role of plasma obestatin levels in obesity which is associated with daily life style in Pakistani population.

Methodology of the study: This cross sectional study was conducted in RHU Centre Tibbi Qaisrani District Dera Ghazi Khan during 2018 to 2019. The data was collected from 100 obese patients which was also suffering from heart and cholesterol diseases.

Results: Mean fasting obestatin levels was 0.450 ± 0.468 and 0.959 ± 0.889 respectively in normal and obese and the difference of mean fasting obestatin levels between the both groups was statistically significant with p value 0.000.

Conclusion: Obestatin plays very important role in obesity and it is directly correlated with blood glucose level.

Corresponding author:**Muhammad Adil Nawaz,**

Rural Health Centre Tibbi Qaisrani District Dera Ghazi Khan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Adil Nawaz et al., *Analysis of Role of Plasma Obestatin Levels in Obesity With Relation To Daily Life Style in Pakistani Population.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is a pathological condition, which results from an imbalance between caloric intake and expenditure, and is characterized by excessive body fat accumulation, that has severe impact on life quality and life expectancy due to the burden of associated comorbidities. Recent data from the World Health Organization suggest that 11% of the world population (more than half a billion people) is obese, while 35% is overweighted [1]. Furthermore, the prevalence of obesity is continuously increasing worldwide, so revealing the patho mechanism and finding effective treatments have become urgent and essential. During the past decades much research has highlighted that neurotransmitter systems controlling appetite and feeding behavior, cognitive function, stress and reward behavior are strongly and reciprocally connected [2]. Food intake is normally regulated by a homeostatic drive to restore energy balance, while in certain conditions hedonic or reward-based regulation favors the consumption of highly palatable, energy-dense foods [3].

Obestatin is a 23-acid metabolic peptide, derived from the preproghrelin gene which was isolated first from the rat stomach in 2005 [4]. However, obestatin is also expressed in other GI organs (pancreas, liver), adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, lungs, thyroid and mammary glands and testes, suggesting a multifunctional role of it, which can act both centrally and peripherally [5]. It was originally described as a direct antagonist of ghrelin with anorexigenic effect. Both central and peripheral injection decreased food intake in a time and dose-dependent manner, body weight gain, and intestinal motility via the G-protein coupled receptor 39 (GPR39) a member of the GHSR family which was

rapidly refuted as a receptor for obestatin by several studies [6].

Aims of the study:

The main aim of the present study is to analyze the role of plasma obestatin levels in obesity which is associated with daily life style.

Methodology of the study:

This cross sectional study was conducted in RHU Centre Tibbi Qaisrani District Dera Ghazi Khan during 2018 to 2019. The data was collected from 100 obese patients which was also suffering from heart and cholesterol diseases. Demographic factors were also asked to the student. Body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC) were done for patients and controls as anthropometrical tests, while fasting serum glucose (FSG) measured using spectrophotometric technique. Each serum sample was analyzed for obestatin hormone and fasting insulin using enzyme linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA).

Statistical analysis:

SPSS analysis test was used in making a comparison of the two-tailed P value of the two groups with a significance set at $p < 0.05$. Results were considered to be of statistical significance if the two-tailed p-value was less than 0.05.

RESULTS:

Mean fasting obestatin levels was 0.450 ± 0.468 and 0.959 ± 0.889 respectively in hypertensive and normotensive obese and the difference of mean fasting obestatin levels between the both groups was statistically significant with p value 0.000.

Table 01: Comparison of mean fasting obestatin levels between hypertensive and normotensive obese

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Hypertensive obese	57	0.450	0.468	0.000
Normotensive obese	57	0.959	0.889	

Table 02: Comparison of mean fasting blood cholesterol levels between normal and obese patients

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Normal	57	206.42	44.420	0.644
Obese patients	57	202.39	48.344	

Mean fasting blood cholesterol level was 206.42 ± 44.420 and 202.39 ± 48.344 respectively in normal and obese and the difference was not statistically significant with p value 0.644.

DISCUSSION:

Hormones and neuropeptides control and integrate the neuro circuits of metabolism, thirst, thermoregulation, and sleep overlapping in the hypothalamus. Accordingly, besides its peripheral effects, central actions of obestatin were also identified [7]. To note first, when administered ICV this peptide inhibited thirst in fed and fasted male rats, and pretreatment with

obestatin also neutralized the dipsogenic effect of angiotensin II. Furthermore, it was also suggested that the anorexigenic effect of this peptide is a consequence of the thirst inhibition, the so called dehydration anorexia [8]. The neurogenesis in the adult hippocampus involves the proliferation, migration and differentiation of progenitor cells. These processes are impaired by different conditions, such as hypoxia, addictive drugs, sustained exposure to stress among others, while certain hormones and growth factors promote the proliferation and survival of the hippocampal neurons.

Obesity has become a major public health problem throughout the world and at least one-third of Arabs are obese, and this figure is rising steadily despite increased interest in fitness. Excess fat accumulation promotes the development of insulin resistance, glucose intolerance and type 2 diabetes mellitus [1-5]. The increasing prevalence of obesity is a serious health concern. Obesity is known to be strongly associated with hypertension and other arteriosclerotic disease, but the pathogenic mechanisms linking hypertension and obesity have not been fully determined. The possible roles of obestatin and ghrelin in obesity and metabolic syndrome have been studied. Changes in the concentrations of these hormones, and in the ghrelin/obestatin ratio, may be risk factors for obesity and hypertension [10].

CONCLUSION:

Obestatin plays very important role in obesity and it is directly correlated with blood glucose level. Furthermore, there was a clear relationship between obestatin and both BP and HOMA-IR, suggesting that obestatin might play a role in BP regulation.

REFERENCES:

- Berthold, HK, Giannakidou, E, Krone, W. Influence of ghrelin gene polymorphisms on hypertension and atherosclerotic disease. *Hypertens Res* 2010; 33: 155–160.
- Gurriarán-Rodríguez, U, Al-Massadi, O, Roca-Rivada, A. Obestatin as a regulator of adipocyte metabolism and adipogenesis. *J Cell Mol Med* 2011; 15: 1927–1940.
- Schulteis G, Yackey M, Risbrough V, Koob GF. Anxiogenic-like effects of spontaneous and naloxone-precipitated opiate withdrawal in the elevated plus-maze. *Pharmacol Biochem Behav.* 1998;60(3):727-31.
- Li T, Hou Y, Cao W, Yan CX, Chen T, Li SB. Naloxone-precipitated withdrawal enhances ERK phosphorylation in prefrontal association cortex

- and accumbens nucleus of morphine-dependent mice. *Neurosci Lett.* 2010;468(3):348-52.
- Vicennati V, Genghini S, and Iasio DR. Circulating obestatin levels and the ghrelin/obestatin ratio in obese women. *European Journal of Endocrinology* 2007; 157: 295–301.
- Taskin MI, Bulbul E, Adali E, Hismiogullari AA, and Inceboz U. Circulating levels of obestatin and co-peptin in obese and non obese women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2015 Jun;189:19-23.
- Yildiz G, Yucel A, Nayon V et al. Evaluation of effects of diet on serum obestatin levels in overweight patients with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Journal of obesity and metabolic research.* 2014;1(4):230-237.
- Dixit, VD, Yang, H, Cooper-Jenkins, A. Reduction of T cell-derived ghrelin enhances proinflammatory cytokine expression: implications for age-associated increases in inflammation. *Blood* 2009; 113: 5202–5205
- Kellokoski, E, Kunnari, A, Jokela, M. Ghrelin and obestatin modulate early atherogenic processes on cells: enhancement of monocyte adhesion and oxidized low-density lipoprotein binding. *Metabolism* 2009; 58: 1572–1580.
- Matthews, DR, Hosker, JP, Rudenski, AS. Homeostasis model assessment: insulin resistance and beta-cell function from fasting plasma glucose and insulin concentrations in man. *Diabetologia* 1985; 28: 412–419.